

Varying Valency of Platinum with respect to Mercaptanic Radicals. Part VIII.

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A good number of compounds by the interaction of chloroplatinic acid with various organic thio compounds (sulphides, mercaptans, disulphides, etc.) has already been described by Rây and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 872; 1922, 121, 1283; 1923, 123, 133; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 178). The action of various bases on some of these complex bodies to elucidate their constitution has also been investigated (*cf.* Rây and collaborators, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 155, 358; 1927, 4, 467; 1928, 5, 139).

In the present paper the action of another organic thio compound, which may be called a 1:4-disulphide, on chloroplatinic acid has been studied and the compound thereof and its derivatives have been subjected to the action of bases (like ethylenediamine, ammonia and pyridine). The resulting products are of much value in elucidating the constitution of the platinum disulphide complexes most of which are insoluble in common solvents.

The 1:4-disulphide employed in preparing platinum complexes has the constitutional formula, $\text{Et S}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{S}\cdot\text{Et}$ (*cf.* Mayer, *Ber.*, 1884, 19, 3266).

By the action of the disulphide upon H_2PtCl_6 , a substance of the approximate composition of $\text{PtCl}_3\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ has been obtained. This insoluble substance (P) may be either $\text{PtCl}_3\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (A) (*cf.* *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 139) or a molecular compound of PtCl_4 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (B) and $\text{PtCl}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (C) (*cf. ibid.*, 1925, 2, 178) or may be a mixture of (B) and (C) in equimolecular proportions approximately. However, the insolubility of the substance (P) in all ordinary solvents prevents its purification or the separation of (B) and (C), if it be a mixture. But both the compounds (B) and (C) have been obtained from (P) (*vide* experimental) by oxidation and reduction respectively, of which (C) is soluble in acetone. The substance (P) on continued boiling with acetone on a water-bath for a few hours gives an acetone extract which leaves

almost nothing on evaporation. This shows that (P) is not a mixture but a distinct chemical compound (with slight impurities) which may be either (A) or the molecular compounds of (B) and (C).

However, by the action of ethylenediamine on the substance (P), a compound $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{En}_2$ (m.p. 308°d.) of known constitution (PtEn_2)- Cl_2 has been obtained by replacing completely the disulphide molecule (*cf.* Jorgensen, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1899, *ii*, 39, 4, 1949). The formation of the above compound can be explained by supposing the mother substance (P) either as (A) (*cf.* *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 467) or as the molecular compound of (B) and (C) (*cf.* the action of NH_3 on $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ *ibid.*, 1926, 3, 155), but both (B) and (C) form the same compound $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{En}_2$ separately with ethylenediamine.

The action of a base of the pyridine type on the substance (P) on continued reflux on a water-bath gives two compounds, one of which has been identified as $[\text{PtPy}_4]\text{Cl}_2$ (m.p. 285°d.), while the other one has approximately the empirical formula $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Py}$; but it could not be obtained in a purer state owing to its insolubility in ordinary solvents. From these results, the molecular formula of (P), though not definitely established, is probably of $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.

The action of dimethylaniline on the substance (P) leads to $[\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{Pt} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2]$ (m.p. 187°) which is soluble only in acetone unlike the original substance (P) (Drew and Wyatt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56).

When $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ is treated with ethylenediamine or with pyridine, the compound $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{En}_2$ (m.p. 308°d.) or $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{Py}$, (m.p. 285°d.) (*cf.* the action of ethylene diamine and pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$) is obtained. The formation of these compounds from $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ supports the molecular formula for $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.

The action of a mild oxidising agent, *e.g.*, the mixture of hydrochloric acid and hydrogen peroxide on $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ converts the latter into $[\text{Cl}_4 \cdot \text{Pt} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2]$.

The action of ethylenediamine on $[\text{Cl}_4 \cdot \text{Pt} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2]$ forms the compound PtEn_2Cl_2 (m.p. 308°d.) and with ammonia, a well known compound of similar type $[\text{Pt} \cdot 4\text{NH}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ (Carlgreen and Cleve, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1892, 1, 67).

But when the substance $[\text{Cl}_4 \cdot \text{Pt} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2]$ is treated with pyridine, a compound of a different type $[\text{Cl}_4 \cdot \text{Pt} \cdot \text{Py}_2]$ is obtained which is insoluble in ordinary solvents,

This supports the constitution of $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ as given above; pyridine only replaces the disulphide molecule, whereas bases like ammonia and ethylenediamine not only replace the disulphide molecule, but also transform, the 6-co-ordinate platinum to a 4-co-ordinate one.

EXPEIRMENTAL.

Action of chloroplatinic acid on the disulphide, $\text{Et} \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{Et}$.—To a strong alcoholic solution of chloroplatinic acid (8 g.) dilute alcoholic solution of the disulphide (3 g.) was added and the mixture gently shaken. The reaction began instantaneously with the separation of an orange coloured insoluble substance which on keeping overnight, was found to be a semi-solid mass. It was transferred on a filter under suction. The residue on the filter was repeatedly washed with alcohol, hot water, alcohol and finally with ether and dried in vacuum. This substance was found to be insoluble in all ordinary solvents, m.p. $168-71^\circ$ (d.) (I). The main filtrate gave another crop after 24 hours and the second crop was isolated as before, m.p. $175-78^\circ$ (d.) (II). In the same way, the third crop was also obtained, m.p. $180-82^\circ$ (d.) (III). All the crops were flesh-coloured and insoluble in ordinary solvents and correspond approximately to the formula $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$. [Found: (I) Cl, 24.07; S, 14.39; Pt 42.7. (II) S, 14.08; Pt, 42.5. (III) S, 14.47; Pt, 42.02. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ requires Cl, 23.58; S, 14.17; Pt, 43.18 per cent].

Action of ethylenediamine on $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.—Ethylenediamine hydrate (5 c.c.) was added to $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (5 g.) in water suspension (20 c.c. of water). After keeping the mixture for 2 days in a closed flask, the whole of $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ went into solution with ether. The aqueous solution thus remained was concentrated to a small volume in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid and precipitated with alcohol. The first crop was precipitated with alcohol and finally crystallised from rectified spirit. This is necessary to free the substance from the hydrochloride of the base that might be formed in the reaction. The substance was brownish in colour m.p. 308° (d.). [Found: N, 14.16; Pt, 50.43. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4 (\text{NH}_2)_2$ requires N, 14.51; Pt, 50.51 per cent].

Action of pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.— $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (5 g.) in alcoholic suspension (25 c.c. alcohol) was refluxed on a water-bath with pyridine in excess (10 c.c.) for 56 hours. The mixture was filtered hot; the filtrate on cooling deposited a crystalline substance which was filtered off and washed several times with ether. The substance is soluble in water, turns yellow at 120° , m.p. 285° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.34; Cl, 11.9; Pt, 33.62. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4 \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires N, 9.62; Cl, 12.19; Pt, 33.5 per cent).

The residue on the filter after filtering the hot mixture was washed several times with hot alcohol and hot water to remove the last traces of the compound $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4 \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$. It was then washed with alcohol, benzene and ether. The substance is insoluble in common organic solvents. It could not be obtained in a very pure state and contained traces of sulphur, m.p. $261\text{--}65^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 23.46; Pt, 40.2. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2 \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Cl, 23.1; Pt, 40.3 per cent).

Action of dimethylaniline on $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.— $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ was treated with a slight excess of dimethylaniline in a hard glass test tube and heated on a water-bath for 2 to 3 hours with occasional stirring. A deep violet solution was obtained which was filtered and to the filtrate excess of an ether-alcohol mixture (1:1) was added, when a precipitate was found to separate. The precipitate thus obtained was dissolved in acetone and reprecipitated with ether. It was then collected and washed several times with alcohol and finally with ether and dried in vacuum. It is a very light greenish substance, m.p. 187° . (Found: Cl, 16.92; S, 15.36; Pt, 47.1. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ requires Cl, 17.06; S, 15.40; Pt, 46.87 per cent).

Action of ethylenediamine on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.—Ethylenediamine (5 c.c.) was added to $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (5 g.) in aqueous suspension (20 c.c. water). After keeping the mixture in a closed flask for a day, whole of $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ went into solution with the liberation of the disulphide which is removed from the mixture by extracting with ether. The aqueous extract on concentration in vacuum over sulphuric acid gave light brownish crystals, m.p. 308° (decomp.) [Found: Pt, 50.32. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ requires Pt, 50.51 per cent].

Action of pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.—To $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ a quantity of pyridine just sufficient to dissolve the substance was added, the solution was diluted with alcohol and allowed to stand for 3 days in a loosely stoppered flask, when a crop of fine white

crystals was found to separate and collected as usual. The substance is soluble in water, becomes yellow at 120° , and melts at 285° , (decomp.). (Found: Pt, 33.41. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4 \text{Py}$ requires Pt, 33.5 per cent).

Preparation of the compound $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.— $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (10 g.) was well triturated with water (120 c.c.) and to this mixture fuming hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) was added, followed by perhydrol (30 c.c.) with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for 2 days in a loosely stoppered flask. The insoluble residue was then collected and washed as usual. The substance is light orange-coloured and insoluble in ordinary solvents and melts at 230° (decomp.). The substance on further treatment with the mixture of fuming hydrochloric acid and perhydrol was found to melt at the same temperature. (Found: Cl, 29.48; S, 12.91; Pt, 39.86. $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ requires Cl, 29.16; S, 13.14; Pt, 40.04 per cent).

Action of ethylenediamine on $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.— $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (3 g.) in aqueous suspension (20 c.c. water) was treated with ethylenediamine hydrate in excess. After allowing the mixture to stand in a closed flask for 3 days, whole of $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ went into solution with the liberation of the disulphide which was removed by extracting with ether. The aqueous extract was then concentrated in vacuum over sulphuric acid to a small volume and precipitated with alcohol. The first crop of the precipitate was redissolved in a small amount of water and reprecipitated with alcohol. It was finally crystallised from rectified spirit. This is necessary to free the substance from the hydrochloride of the base that might be formed in the reaction. The substance is brownish in colour and melts at 308° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.32; Cl, 18.5; Pt, 50.6. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2 \text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ requires N, 14.51; Cl, 18.39; Pt, 50.51 per cent).

The ionisability of $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{En}_2$ (Precipitation method).—The substance was dissolved in water and AgNO_3 solution added in the cold without adding nitric acid. The result obtained is slightly low. [Found: Cl, 17.89. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{En}_2$ (assuming both Cl_2 atoms ionisable) requires Cl, 18.39 per cent).

Action of ammonia on $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.— $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (5 g.) was covered with liquor ammonia (25 c.c.) and the mixture was kept in a stoppered flask with occasional shaking. After 2 days, whole of the $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ went into solution with the liberation of the disulphide which was removed by extracting with ether. The aqueous extract was concentrated to a small volume in vacuum and

precipitated with alcohol. The precipitate was collected and the process of solution in water and precipitation with alcohol was repeated twice. The substance is light brownish and very hygroscopic. (Found: Cl, 21.17; Pt, 58.15. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$ requires Cl, 21.26; Pt, 58.38 per cent).

Action of pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_6 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$.— $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2$ (6 g.) in alcoholic suspension (100 c.c. alcohol) was treated with pyridine (15 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 12 hours, when the light orange colour of the compound gradually changed into light yellow. The yellow compound was collected and washed as usual, m.p. 270° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.34; Cl, 84.28; Pt, 39.27. $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ requires N, 5.67; Cl, 28.68; Pt, 39.4 per cent).

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